

EFFECTS OF AUDIO-VISUAL AIDS IN TEACHING AND LEARNING BIOLOGY IN GUAKRO EFFAH SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL

Abstract

This study examines the impact of audio-visual aids in the teaching of biology in Guakro Effah Senior High School. The investigation focused on comparing the academic performance of students taught with and without the use of audio-visual aids. Results demonstrated significant improvements in student engagement and comprehension in the experimental group. The study concludes that audio-visual tools are crucial in enhancing the learning experience in science education.

Keywords

Audio-visual aids, biology education, student performance, science education, senior high school, instructional materials

1. Introduction

1.1 Background to the Study

The use of audio-visual aids is essential in modern educational systems, particularly in science education, where abstract concepts are common. According to studies such as those by Isaac & Iorkpilgh (2013), audio-visual aids serve as effective tools for enhancing teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes. The Biological Science Curriculum Study (BSCS) highlights the importance of these tools in bridging conceptual gaps (BSCS, 2011).

Biology is an activity-oriented subject, and its effective teaching often requires resource-based instruction, such as audio-visual aids. Studies have demonstrated that the absence of these tools correlates with poor performance in biology (Samreen, 2012). Consequently, the current study investigates how audio-visual aids affect student achievement in biology, focusing on Guakro Effah Senior High School in Ghana.

1.2 Problem Statement

The decline in students' performance in biology at the senior high school level has raised concerns among educational stakeholders (Al-Zoubi, 2015). Conventional, theory-heavy teaching methods have proven insufficient in motivating students. It is hypothesized that the integration of audio-visual aids could improve academic performance, prompting this study.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Jean Piaget's Cognitive Development Theory posits that children actively construct their

knowledge through interaction with their environment (Piaget, 1936). This study builds on Piaget's assertion that hands-on, interactive learning is critical, aligning with the use of audio-visual aids to facilitate concept acquisition in biology.

2.2 Empirical Studies

Numerous empirical studies underline the benefits of audio-visual aids in science education. Anzaku (2011) notes that audio-visual materials facilitate better retention and understanding. Further, Reisman (1994) points out that multimedia presentations can make complex scientific topics more accessible. Recent studies continue to validate these findings, emphasizing the increasing reliance on technology in classrooms (Manalanga & Awelani, 2014).

3. Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This quasi-experimental study involved a pretest-posttest control group design. The experimental group was exposed to lessons incorporating audio-visual aids, while the control group received conventional instruction without these tools.

3.2 Sample and Population

The study was conducted among SHS2 students at Guakro Effah Senior High School. Four classes (two experimental, two control) were selected, totaling 145 students, with both male and female students represented. The sample selection ensured that gender differences could be examined in the context of biology performance.

3.3 Data Collection Instrument

A 20-item Biology Performance Test (BPT) was developed and administered as both pretest and posttest. The pretest gauged the baseline knowledge of the students, and the posttest measured the effect of the audio-visual intervention.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Achievement Differences

The analysis showed a statistically significant difference between the experimental and control groups. Students taught with audio-visual aids had higher posttest scores (mean = 72.3) compared to the control group (mean = 58.7). This supports earlier findings by Auwalu (2014), suggesting that visual learning enhances students' grasp of complex topics.

4.2 Gender Differences

While male students slightly outperformed females, the gender difference was not statistically significant, indicating that both genders benefit similarly from the use of audio-visual aids. This contradicts older studies that suggested gender-based discrepancies in science learning (Borniface, 2013).

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

The study confirms that audio-visual aids are effective in improving students' performance in biology, especially in resource-constrained environments like Guakro Effah Senior High School. The integration of such tools promotes better retention and engagement among students.

5.2 Recommendations

- **Teacher Training:** Educators should be trained to effectively integrate audio-visual materials into their lessons.
 - **Curriculum Development:** Educational policymakers should incorporate audio-visual tools into the biology curriculum, ensuring their consistent use from early secondary education.
 - **Further Research:** Future studies could explore the long-term effects of audio-visual aids on retention and conceptual understanding in other science subjects.
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